

FEATURE LEARNING FOR CHORD RECOGNITION: THE DEEP CHROMA EXTRACTOR

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ABSTRACT

We explore frame-level audio feature learning for chord recognition using artificial neural networks. We present the argument that chroma vectors potentially hold enough information to model harmonic content of audio for chord recognition, but that standard chroma extractors compute too noisy features. This leads us to propose a learned chroma feature extractor based on artificial neural networks. It is trained to compute chroma features that encode harmonic information important for chord recognition, while being robust to irrelevant interferences. We achieve this by feeding the network an audio spectrum with context instead of a single frame as input. This way, the network can learn to selectively compensate noise and resolve harmonic ambiguities.

We compare the resulting features to hand-crafted ones by using a simple linear frame-wise classifier for chord recognition on various data sets. The results show that the learned feature extractor produces superior chroma vectors for chord recognition.

1. INTRODUCTION

Chord Recognition (CR) has been an active research field since its inception by Fujishima in 1999 [10]. Since then, researchers have explored many aspects of this field, and developed various systems to automatically extract chords from audio recordings of music (see [20] for a recent review). Chord recognition meets this great interest in the MIR (music information research) community because harmonic content is a descriptive mid-level feature of (Western) music that can be used directly (e.g. for creating lead sheets for musicians) and as basis for higher-level tasks such as cover song identification, key detection or harmonic analysis.

Most chord recognition systems follow a common pipeline of feature extraction, pattern matching, and chord sequence decoding (also called *post-filtering*) [7]. In this paper, we focus on the first step in this pipeline: feature extraction.

Two observations lead us to explore better features for chord recognition: (1) *The capabilities of chord models for pattern matching are limited*. In [7], Cho and Bello conclude that appropriate features largely redeem the benefits of complex chord models. (2) *The capabilities of post-filtering are limited*. As shown in [6, 7], post-filtering methods are useful because they enforce continuity of individual chords rather than providing information about chord transitions. Incorporating such information did not considerably improve recognition results in both studies. Chen et al. [6] also observed quantitatively that in popular music “chord progressions are less predictable than it seems”, and thus knowing chord history does not greatly narrow the possibilities for the next chord. Given these apparent limitations of the pattern matching and post-filtering stages, it is not surprising that they only partly compensate the performance gap between features [7]. We therefore have to compute better features if we want to improve chord recognition.

In this paper, we take a step towards better features for chord recognition by introducing a data-driven approach to extract chromagrams that specifically encode content relevant to harmony. Our method learns to discard irrelevant information like percussive noise, overtones or timbral variations automatically from data. We argue that it is thus able to compensate a broader range of interferences than hand-crafted approaches.

2. CHROMAGRAMS

The most popular feature used for chord recognition is the *Chromagram*. A chromagram comprises a time-series of chroma vectors, which represent harmonic content at a specific time in the audio as $c \in \mathbb{R}^{12}$. Each c_i stands for a pitch class, and its value indicates the current saliency of the corresponding pitch class. Chroma vectors are computed by applying a filter bank to a time-frequency representation of the audio. This representation results from either a short-time Fourier transform (STFT) or a constant-q transform (CQT), the latter being more popular due to a finer frequency resolution in the lower frequency area.

Chromagrams are concise descriptors of harmony because they encode tone quality and neglect tone height. In theory, this limits their representational power: without octave information, one cannot distinguish e.g. chords that comprise the same pitch classes, but have a different bass note (like G vs. G/5, or A:sus2 vs. E:sus4). In prac-

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tice, we can show that given chromagrams derived from ground truth annotations, using logistic regression we can recognise 97% of chords (reduced to major/minor) in the Beatles dataset. This result encourages us to create chroma features that contain harmony information, but are robust to spectral content that is harmonically irrelevant.

Chroma features are noisy in their basic formulation because they are affected by various interferences: musical instruments produce overtones in addition to the fundamental frequency; percussive instruments pollute the spectrogram with broadband frequency activations (e.g. snare drums) and/or pitch-like sounds (tom-toms, bass drums); different combinations of instruments (and different, possibly genre-dependent mixing techniques) create different timbres and thus increase variance [7, 20].

Researchers have developed and used an array of methods that mitigate these problems and extract cleaner chromagrams: Harmonic-percussive source separation can filter out broadband frequency responses of percussive instruments [22, 27], various methods tackle interferences caused by overtones [7, 19], while [21, 27] attempt to extract chromas robust to timbre. See [7] for a recent overview and evaluation of different methods for chroma extraction. Although these approaches improve the quality of extracted chromas, it is very difficult to hand-craft methods for all conceivable disturbances, even if we could name and quantify them.

The approaches mentioned above share a common limitation: they mostly operate on single feature frames. Single frames are often not enough to decide which frequencies salient in the spectrum are relevant to harmony and which are noise. This is usually countered by contextual aggregation such as moving mean/median filters or beat synchronisation, which are supposed to smooth out noisy frames. Since they operate only *after* computing the chromas, they address the symptoms (noisy frames) but do not tackle the cause (spectral content irrelevant to harmony). Also, [7] found that they blur chord boundaries and details in a signal and can impair results when combined with more complex chord models and post-filtering methods.

It is close to impossible to find the rules or formulas that define harmonic relevance of spectral content manually. We thus resort to the data-driven approach of deep learning. Deep learning was found to extract strong, hierarchical, discriminative features [1] in many domains. Deep learning based systems established new state-of-the-art results in computer vision¹, speech recognition, and MIR tasks such as beat detection [3], tempo estimation [4] or structural segmentation [28].

In this paper, we want to exploit the power of deep neural networks to compute harmonically relevant chroma features. The proposed chroma extractor learns to filter harmonically irrelevant spectral content from a *context of audio frames*. This way, we circumvent the necessity to temporally smooth the features by allowing the chroma extractor to use context information directly. Our method

computes cleaner chromagrams while retaining their advantages of low dimensionality and intuitive interpretation.

3. RELATED WORK

A number of works used neural networks in the context of chord recognition. Humphrey and Bello [14] applied Convolutional Neural Networks to classify major and minor chords end-to-end. Boulanger-Lewandowski et al. [5], and Sigtia et al. [24] explored Recurrent Neural Networks as a post-filtering method, where the former used a deep belief net, the latter a deep neural network as underlying feature extractor. All these approaches train their models to directly predict major and minor chords, and following [1], the hidden layers of these models learn a hierarchical, discriminative feature representation. However, since the models are trained to distinguish major/minor chords only, they consider other chord types (such as seventh, augmented, or suspended) mapped to major/minor as intra-class variation to be robust against, which will be reflected by the extracted internal features. These features might thus not be useful to recognise other chords.

We circumvent this by using chroma templates derived from chords as distributed (albeit incomplete) representation of chords. Instead of directly classifying a chord label, the network is required to compute the *chroma representation* of a chord given the corresponding spectrogram. We expect the network to learn which saliency in the spectrogram is responsible for a certain pitch class to be harmonically important, and compute higher values for the corresponding elements of the output chroma vector.

Approaches to directly learn a mapping from spectrogram to chroma include those by İzmirlı and Dannenberg [29] and Chen et al. [6]. However, both learn only a linear transformation of the time-frequency representation, which limits the mapping’s expressivity. Additionally, both base their mapping on a single frame, which comes with the disadvantages we outlined in the previous section.

In an alternative approach, Humphrey et al. apply deep learning methods to produce Tonnetz features from a spectrogram [15]. Using other features than the chromagram is a promising direction, and was also explored in [6] for bass notes. Most chord recognition systems however still use chromas, and more research is necessary to explore to which degree and under which circumstances Tonnetz features are favourable.

4. METHOD

To construct a robust chroma feature extractor, we use a deep neural network (DNN). DNNs consist of L hidden layers h_l of U_l computing units. These units compute values based on the results of the previous layer, such that

$$h_l(x) = \sigma_l(W_l \cdot h_{l-1}(x) + b_l), \quad (1)$$

where x is the input to the net, $W_l \in \mathbb{R}^{U_l \times U_{l-1}}$ and $b_l \in \mathbb{R}^{U_l}$ are the weights and the bias of the l^{th} layer re-

¹ See https://rodrigob.github.io/are_we_there_yet/build/classification_datasets_results.html for results on computer vision.

spectively, and σ_l is a (usually non-linear) *activation function* applied point-wise.

We define two additional special layers: an *input layer* that is feeding values to h_1 as $h_0(x) = x$, with U_0 being the input’s dimensionality; and an *output layer* h_{L+1} that takes the same form as shown in Eq. 1, but has a specific semantic purpose: it represents the output of the network, and thus its dimensionality U_{L+1} and activation function σ_{L+1} have to be set accordingly.²

The weights and biases constitute the model’s parameters. They are trained in a supervised manner by gradient methods and error back-propagation in order to minimise the loss of the network’s output. The loss function depends on the domain, but is generally some measure of difference between the current output and the desired output (e.g. mean squared error, categorical cross-entropy, etc.)

In the following, we describe how we compute the input to the DNN, the concrete DNN architecture and how it was trained.

4.1 Input Processing

We compute the time-frequency representation of the signal based on the magnitude of its STFT X . The STFT gives significantly worse results than the constant-q transform if used as basis for traditional chroma extractors, but we found in preliminary experiments that our model is not sensitive to this phenomenon. We use a frame size of 8192 with a hop size of 4410 at a sample rate of 44100 Hz. Then, we apply triangular filters to convert the linear frequency scale of the magnitude spectrogram to a logarithmic one in what we call the *quarter-tone spectrogram* $S = F_{Log}^\Delta \cdot |X|$, where F_{Log}^Δ is the filter bank. The quarter-tone spectrogram contains only bins corresponding to frequencies between 30 Hz and 5500 Hz and has 24 bins per octave. This results in a dimensionality of 178 bins. Finally, we apply a logarithmic compression such that $S_{log} = \log(1 + S)$, which we will call the *logarithmic quarter-tone spectrogram*. To be concise, we will refer to S_{log} as “spectrogram” in rest of this paper.

Our model uses a context window around a target frame as input. Through systematic experiments on the validation folds (see Sec.5.1) we found a context window of ± 0.7 s to work best. Since we operate at 10 fps, we feed our network at each time 15 consecutive frames, which we will denote as *super-frame*.

4.2 Model

We define the model architecture and set the model’s hyper-parameters based on validation performance in several preliminary experiments. Although a more systematic approach might reveal better configurations, we found that results do not vary by much once we reach a certain model complexity.

² For example, for a 3-class classification problem one would use 3 units in the output layer and a softmax activation function such that the network’s output can be interpreted as probability distribution of classes given the data.

Figure 1. Model overview. At each time 15 consecutive frames of the input quarter-tone spectrogram S_{Log} are fed to a series of 3 dense layers of 512 rectifier units, and finally to a sigmoid output layer of 12 units (one per pitch class), which represents the chroma vector for the centre input frame.

Our model is a deep neural network with 3 hidden layers of 512 rectifier units [11] each. Thus, $\sigma_l(x) = \max(0, x)$ for $1 \leq l \leq L$. The output layer, representing the chroma vector, consists of 12 units (one unit per pitch class) with a sigmoid activation function $\sigma_{L+1}(x) = 1/(1+\exp(-x))$. The input layer represents the input super-frame and thus has a dimensionality of 2670. Fig. 1 shows an overview of our model.

4.3 Training

To train the network, we propagate back through the network the gradient of the loss \mathcal{L} with relation to the network parameters. Our loss is the binary cross-entropy between each pitch class in the predicted chroma vector $\mathbf{p} = h_{L+1}(S_{log})$ and the target chroma vector \mathbf{t} , which is derived from the ground truth chord label. For a single data instance,

$$\mathcal{L} = \frac{1}{12} \sum_{i=1}^{12} -t_i \log(p_i) - (1 - t_i) \log(1 - p_i). \quad (2)$$

We learn the parameters with mini-batch training (batch size 512) using the ADAM update rule [16]. We also tried simple stochastic gradient descent with Nesterov momentum and a number of manual learn rate schedules, but could not achieve better results (to the contrary, using ADAM training usually converged earlier). To prevent over-fitting, we apply dropout [26] with probability 0.5 after each hidden layer and early stopping if validation accuracy does not increase after 20 epochs.

5. EXPERIMENTS

To evaluate the chroma features our method produces, we set up a simple chord recognition task. We ignore any post-filtering methods and use a simple, linear classifier (logistic regression) to match features to chords. This way we want to isolate the effect of the feature on recognition accuracy. As it is common, we restrict ourselves to distinct only major/minor chords, resulting in 24 chord classes and a ‘no chord’ class.

Figure 2. Validation WCSR for Major/minor chord recognition of different methods given different audio context sizes. Whiskers represent 0.95 confidence intervals.

Our compound evaluation dataset comprises the Beatles [13], Queen and Zweieck [18] datasets (which form the “Isophonics” dataset used in the MIREX³ competition), the RWC pop dataset⁴ [12], and the Robbie Williams dataset [8]. The datasets total 383 songs or approx. 21 hours and 39 minutes of music.

We perform 8-fold cross validation with random splits. For the Beatles dataset, we ensure that each fold has the same album distribution. For each test fold, we use six of the remaining folds for training and one for validation.

As evaluation measure, we compute the Weighted Chord Symbol Recall (WCSR), often called Weighted Average Overlap Ratio (WAOR) of major and minor chords using the `mir_eval` library [23].

5.1 Compared Features

We evaluate our extracted features C_D against three baselines: a standard chromagram C computed from a constant-q transform, a chromagram with frequency weighting and logarithmic compression of the underlying constant-q transform C_{Log}^W , and the quarter-tone spectrogram S_{Log} . The chromagrams are computed using the `librosa` library⁵. Their parametrisation follows closely the suggestions in [7], where C_{Log}^W was found to be the best chroma feature for chord recognition.

Each baseline can take advantage of context information. Instead of computing a running mean or median, we allow logistic regression to consider multiple frames of each feature⁶. This is a more general way to incorporate context, because running mean is a subset of the context aggregation functions possible in our setup. Since training logistic regression is a convex problem, the result is at least as good as if we used a running mean.

³ <http://www.music-ir.org/mirex>

⁴ Chord annotations available at <https://github.com/tmc323/Chord-Annotations>

⁵ <https://github.com/bmcfee/librosa>

⁶ Note that this description applies only to the baseline methods. For our DNN feature extractor, “context” means the amount of context the DNN sees. The logistic regression always sees only one frame of the feature the DNN computed.

	Btls	Iso	RWC	RW	Total
C	71.0±0.1	69.5 ±0.1	67.4±0.2	71.1±0.1	69.2±0.1
C_{Log}^W	76.0±0.1	74.2 ±0.1	70.3±0.3	74.4±0.2	73.0±0.1
S_{Log}	78.0±0.2	76.5 ±0.2	74.4±0.4	77.8±0.4	76.1±0.2
C_D	80.2±0.1	79.3±0.1	77.3±0.1	80.1±0.1	78.8±0.1

Table 1. Cross-validated WCSR on the Maj/min task of compared methods on various datasets. Best results are bold-faced ($p < 10^{-9}$). Small numbers indicate standard deviation over 10 experiments. “Btls” stands for the Beatles, “Iso” for Isophonics, and “RW” for the Robbie Williams datasets. Note that the Isophonics dataset comprises the Beatles, Queen and Zweieck datasets.

We determined the optimal amount of context for each baseline experimentally using the validation folds, as shown in Fig. 2. The best results achieved were 79.0% with 1.5 s context for C_D , 76.8% with 1.1 s context for S_{Log} , 73.3% with 3.1 s context for C_{Log}^W , and 69.5% with 2.7 s context for C . We fix these context lengths for testing.

6. RESULTS

Table 1 presents the results of our method compared to the baselines on several datasets. The chroma features C and C_{Log}^W achieve results comparable to those [7] reported on a slightly different compound dataset. Our proposed feature extractor C_D clearly performs best, with $p < 10^{-9}$ according to a paired t-test. The results indicate that the chroma vectors extracted by the proposed method are better suited for chord recognition than those computed by the baselines.

To our surprise, the raw quarter-tone spectrogram S_{Log} performed better than the chroma features. This indicates that computing chroma vectors in the traditional way mixes harmonically relevant features found in the time-frequency representation with irrelevant ones, and the final classifier cannot disentangle them. This raises the question of why chroma features are preferred to spectrograms in the first place. We speculate that the main reason is their much lower dimensionality and thus ease of modelling (e.g. using Gaussian mixtures).

Artificial neural networks often give good results, but it is difficult to understand what they learned, or on which basis they generate their output. In the following, we will try to dissect the proposed model, understand its workings, and see what it pays attention to. To this end, we compute saliency maps using guided back-propagation [25], adapting code freely available⁷ for the Lasagne library [9]. Leaving out the technical details, a saliency map can be interpreted as an attention map of the same size as the input. The higher the absolute saliency at a specific input dimension, the stronger its influence on the output, where positive values indicate a direct relationship, negative values an indirect one.

Fig. 3 shows a saliency map and its corresponding super-frame, representing a C major chord. As expected,

⁷ <https://github.com/Lasagne/Recipes/>

Figure 3. Input example (C major chord) with corresponding saliency map. The *left image* shows the spectrogram frames fed into the network. The *centre image* shows the corresponding saliency map, where red pixels represent positive, blue pixels negative values. The stronger the saturation, the higher the absolute value. The *right plot* shows the saliency summed over the time axis, and thus how each frequency bin influences the output. Note the strong positive influences of frequency bins corresponding to *c*, *e*, and *g* notes that form a C major chord.

the saliency map shows that the most relevant parts of the input are close to the target frame and in the mid frequencies. Here, frequency bins corresponding to notes contained in a C major chord (*c*, *e*, and *g*) showing positive saliency peaks, with the third, *e*, standing out as the strongest. Conversely, its neighbouring semitone, *f*, exhibits strong negative saliency values. Fig. 4 depicts average saliencies for two chords computed over the whole Beatles corpus.

Fig. 5 shows the average saliency map over all superframes of the Beatles dataset summed over the frequency axis. It thus shows the magnitude with which individual frames in the super-frame contribute to the output of the neural network. We observe that most information is drawn from a ± 0.3 s window around the centre frame. This is in line with the results shown in Fig. 2, where the proposed method already performed well with 0.7 s of audio context.

Fig. 6 shows the average saliency map over all superframes of the Beatles dataset, and its sum over the time axis. We observe that frequency bins below 110 Hz and above 3136 Hz (wide limits) are almost irrelevant, and that the net focuses mostly on the frequency range between 196 Hz and 1319 Hz (narrow limits). In informal experiments, we could confirm that recognition accuracy drops only marginally if we restrict the frequency range to the wide limits, but significantly if we restrict it to the narrow

Figure 4. Average saliency map summed over the time axis for A:min7 and F#:min chords computed on the Beatles dataset. As expected, we observe mostly positive peaks for frequency bins corresponding to notes present in the chords (*a*, *c*, *e*, *g* for A:min7; *f#*, *a*, *c#* for F#:min).

Figure 5. Average positive and negative saliencies of all input frames of the Beatles dataset, summed over the frequency axis. Most of the important information is within ± 0.3 s around the centre frame, and past data seems to be more important than future data. Around the centre frame, the network pays relatively more attention to what should be *missing* than present in a given chroma vector, and vice versa in areas further away from the centre. The differences are statistically significant due to the large number of samples.

limits. This means that the secondary information captured by the additional frequency bins of the wide limits is also crucial.

To allow for a visual comparison of the computed features, we depict different chromagrams for the song “Yesterday” by the Beatles in Fig. 7. The images show that the chroma vectors extracted by the proposed method are less noisy and chord transitions are crisper compared to the baseline methods.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we presented a data-driven approach to learning a neural-network-based chroma extractor for chord recognition. The proposed extractor computes cleaner chromagrams than state-of-the-art baseline methods, which we showed quantitatively in a simple chord recognition experiment and examined qualitatively by visually comparing extracted chromagrams.

We inspected the learned model using saliency maps and found that a frequency range of 110 Hz to 3136 Hz

Figure 6. Average saliency of all input frames of the Beatles dataset (bottom image), summed over the time axis (top plot). We see that most relevant information can be collected in barely 3 octaves between G3 at 196 Hz and E6 at 1319 Hz. Hardly any harmonic information resides below 110 Hz and above 3136 Hz. The plot is spiky at frequency bins that correspond to clean semitones because most of the songs in the dataset seem to be tuned to a reference frequency of 440 Hz. The network thus usually pays little attention to the frequency bins between semitones.

Figure 7. Excerpts of chromagrams extracted from the song “Yesterday” by the Beatles. The *lower image* shows chroma computed by the C_{Log}^W without smoothing. We see a good temporal resolution, but also noise. The centre image shows the same chromas after a moving average filter of 1.5 seconds. The filter reduced noise considerably, at the cost blurring chord transitions. The upper plot shows the chromagram extracted by our proposed method. It displays precise pitch activations and low noise, while keeping chord boundaries crisp. Pixel values are scaled such that for each image, the lowest value in the respective chromagram is mapped to white, the highest to black.

seems to suffice as input to chord recognition methods. Using saliency maps and preliminary experiments on validation folds we also found that a context of 1.5 seconds is adequate for local harmony estimation.

There are plenty possibilities for future work to extend and/or improve our method. To achieve better results, we could use DNN ensembles instead of a single DNN. We could ensure that the network sees data for which its predictions are wrong more often during training, or similarly, we could simulate a more balanced dataset by showing the net super-frames of rare chords more often. To further assess how useful the extracted features are for chord recognition, we shall investigate how well they interact with post-filtering methods; since the feature extractor is trained discriminatively, Conditional Random Fields [17] would be a natural choice.

Finally, we believe that the proposed method extracts features that are useful in any other MIR applications that use chroma features (e.g. structural segmentation, key estimation, cover song detection). To facilitate respective experiments, we provide source code for our method as part of the *madmom* audio processing framework [2]. Information and source code to reproduce our experiments can be found at <http://www.cp.jku.at/people/korzeniowski/dc>.

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